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LOAN PORTFOLIO OF BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN AND WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF LOAN PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Decreasing the share of non-performing loans is critical for ensuring financial stability, enhancing credit availability, improving cost efficiency, strengthening risk management, fostering investor confidence, complying with regulatory requirements, and supporting sustainable economic growth. By addressing the root causes of NPLs and implementing effective risk mitigation strategies, banks can enhance their resilience, competitiveness, and long-term viability in the global financial landscape. The paper examines the essence of the concept of problem loans, presents the main factors that contribute to the emergence of NPLs and deals with the analysis of the quality of the loan portfolio of banks in Uzbekistan. Moreover, the paper presents proposals for improving the efficiency of managing the loan portfolio of commercial banks.

Key words: banks, banking system, loans, loan portfolio, problem assets, profitability, loan portfolio management, loan portfolio quality, risks.

Annotatsiya: Noto'lovchi kreditlar ulushini kamaytirish moliyaviy barqarorlikni ta'minlash, kredit olish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish, xarajatlarni optimallashtirish, risklarni boshqarishni mustahkamlash, investorlar ishonchini oshirish, tartibga soluvchi talablarga rioya qilish va barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. NPL'larning asosiy sabablarini bartaraf etish va samarali risklarni kamaytirish strategiyalarini joriy qilish orqali banklar o'zining chidamliligini, raqobatbardoshligini va global moliyaviy maydondagi uzoq muddatli barqarorligini ta'minlashi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada muammoli kreditlar tushunchasi, NPL'larning yuzaga kelishiga olib keluvchi asosiy omillar va O'zbekiston banklarining kredit portfeli sifatini tahlil qilish yoritilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada tijorat banklari kredit portfelini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: banklar, bank tizimi, kreditlar, kredit portfeli, muammoli aktivlar, rentabellik, kredit portfelini boshqarish, kredit portfeli sifati, risklar.

Аннотация: Снижение доли проблемных кредитов имеет критическое значение для обеспечения финансовой стабильности, расширения возможностей кредитования, повышения эффективности затрат, укрепления управления рисками, повышения доверия инвесторов, соблюдения нормативных требований и поддержки устойчивого экономического роста. Устраняя коренные причины проблемных кредитов и внедряя эффективные стратегии снижения рисков, банки могут укрепить свою устойчивость, конкурентоспособность и долгосрочную жизнеспособность в глобальном финансовом пространстве. В статье исследуется сущность понятия проблемных кредитов, рассматриваются основные факторы, способствующие их возникновению, а также проводится анализ качества кредитного портфеля банков Узбекистана. Кроме того, в статье представлены предложения по повышению эффективности управления кредитным портфелем коммерческих банков.

Ключевые слова: банки, банковская система, кредиты, кредитный портфель, проблемные активы, прибыльность, управление кредитным портфелем, качество кредитного портфеля, риски.

INTRODUCTION

The stability and efficiency of the banking sector are fundamental to the overall health and prosperity of an economy. Central to this stability is the management of loan portfolios, which serve as the lifeblood of financial institutions, facilitating economic activity and growth through the allocation of capital. However, a persistent

challenge facing banks worldwide is the issue of non-performing loans (NPLs), often referred to as bad loans or troubled assets. Non-performing bank loans are loans on which borrowers have failed to make scheduled payments for a specified period, typically 90 days or more [1].

There are several definitions of distressed assets in the academic literature. In some literature, risky credit investments in the activity of commercial banks are defined as investments in the form of problem assets, while in some literature, problem assets are defined as a loan that the bank has doubts about its object, subject and provision. Also, if the given loan has non-performing collateral and the value of this collateral is less than the outstanding debt, then this loan is considered a non-performing asset.

Problem assets are assets which quality is classified as “unsatisfactory”, “doubtful” and “hopeless”. In its economic essence, problem assets are the result of the actual manifestation of credit risks, that is, the consequence of not being able to properly manage credit risks.

Problem assets do not occur all at once, but their elements begin to appear gradually during the lending process [2]. Problem assets also occur as a result of a lack of continuous monitoring.

The prevalence of non-performing bank loans can have far-reaching consequences, both for financial institutions and the broader economy [3]. For banks, NPLs can erode profitability, impair capital adequacy, and pose significant credit risk.

Moreover, the management and resolution of non-performing loans can be complex, requiring dedicated resources and strategies to mitigate potential losses and restore financial health.

Beyond the banking sector, the presence of high levels of non-performing loans can impede credit availability, constrain economic growth, and undermine financial stability [4].

Inefficient allocation of capital, reduced lending capacity, and heightened risk aversion can stifle investment, entrepreneurship, and consumption, hindering economic recovery and development [5].

Against this backdrop, understanding the drivers, dynamics, and implications of non-performing bank loans is of paramount importance for policymakers, regulators, investors, and stakeholders alike.

The paper is structured as follows: In Section 1, we introduce the present research. Section 2 outlines the methodology used to gather and identify pertinent papers for examination. Section 3 presents the analysis outcomes. Section 4 discusses the finding of this study. Lastly, in Section 5, we offer conclusions based on the research conducted.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Loan portfolio management is a critical component of a bank’s overall financial strategy, as it directly influences both profitability and risk exposure. Effective management of loan portfolios ensures that banks maintain a balance between achieving high returns and mitigating risks associated with loan defaults. Globally, research has shown that loan portfolio diversification, robust risk assessment models, and enhanced regulatory frameworks play significant roles in improving the efficiency of loan portfolio management (Mishkin, 2018).

In Uzbekistan, the banking sector is undergoing significant reforms to align with international standards. A key focus has been on enhancing the management of loan portfolios to improve financial stability and economic growth. According to Uzbek economist R. Sodikov, the efficiency of loan portfolio management in Uzbekistan is still developing. He argues that a critical area for improvement is the adoption of advanced risk management techniques, such as credit scoring models and predictive analytics, which can help banks better assess borrower risk and minimize non-performing loans (Sodikov, 2020). Sodikov’s research highlights the need for Uzbek banks to invest in modern technologies and financial tools to optimize their loan portfolios and ensure long-term sustainability.

Furthermore, international literature suggests that the application of digital solutions, such as fintech platforms and big data analytics, can significantly enhance the efficiency of loan portfolio management. Studies conducted by the World Bank emphasize the importance of adopting digital risk assessment tools, which allow for more accurate credit evaluations and real-time monitoring of loan performance. The implementation of such tools in developing economies like Uzbekistan can help reduce the incidence of bad loans and increase the overall profitability of banks (World Bank, 2021).

Another aspect of loan portfolio management is the regulatory environment. In Uzbekistan, recent reforms have been aimed at strengthening the legal framework governing bank lending practices. The introduction of more stringent regulations and reporting requirements is expected to improve transparency and accountability in loan portfolio management. Studies indicate that effective regulatory oversight plays a crucial role in minimizing systemic risks and promoting sound banking practices (OECD, 2022).

In conclusion, the literature highlights the importance of advanced risk management tools, digital innovation, and strong regulatory frameworks in improving the efficiency of loan portfolio management in Uzbekistan. As the banking sector continues to evolve, adopting global best practices and investing in modern financial

technologies will be essential for maintaining financial stability and enhancing the performance of loan portfolios.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were used. The use of deductive or inductive methods in the order from generality to individuality and vice versa is effective in studying the subject, and the method of abstract-logical thinking is important in the systematic analysis of the process. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Problem assets do not occur all at once, but their elements begin to appear gradually during the lending process [6]. Problem assets also occur as a result of a lack of continuous monitoring.

Problem assets can have different causes. According to the World Bank, 67% of losses are caused by internal factors in the occurrence of problematic assets of banks. This indicator is only 33% according to external factors.

Table 1. Factors affecting the origin of problem assets.

Influencing factors	Exposure rate (%)
Internal factors	67 %
Lack of supply	22 %
Incorrect evaluation of information in the study of credit order	21 %
Weakness of operational control and failure to detect early warning signs in time and not take appropriate measures in relation to them	18 %
Low quality of collateral	5 %
Inability to obtain the provision specified in the contract	1 %
External factors	33 %
Bankruptcy of the company	12 %
Demanding creditors to repay the debt	11 %
Loss of the company's position in the market and internal social problems	6 %
Theft, fraud	4 %

Some of the reasons for the emergence of problem assets may be related to the activities of the debtor customer, while others may be related to the activities of the bank.

Non-performing assets usually occur when the borrower does not have enough cash to repay the loan. In some cases, they may also occur when the client does not want to pay the loan when there are funds in the account. When there is a possibility of problem assets, banks create mandatory reserves designed to cover possible losses.

The sharp decline in the quality of the loan portfolio can be linked to the significant downturn in economic activity and the resulting stagnation in credit. This was partly caused by the restricted access of banks in the region to wholesale borrowing markets, which led to a substantial drop in their profitability [7].

Fig.1. Problem loans of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2023 (in billion soums).

From the data of Fig. 1, the share of problem loans in the credit portfolio of commercial banks was 2.10% as of January 1, 2021, and as of January 1, 2022, this indicator increased by 3.11 percentage points to 5.2%. The loan portfolio of domestic commercial banks increased by 117.84% in 2021 compared to 2020.

As of January 1, 2021, the amount of non-performing loans (NPL) in the credit portfolio of commercial banks was 5,784.83 billion soums, and as of January 1, 2022, this figure reached 16,974.03 billion soums.

As of January 1, 2023, the gross loan portfolio of banks amounted to 390,049.0 billion soums. In it, the weight of problem assets decreased by 1.6% compared to the beginning of 2022 and amounted to 3.6%.

By the end of 2023, positive dynamics are observed in the credit portfolio of banks an increase of 1.21 times is observed. In this, the share of NPLs decreased by 2,629.0 billion soums, and their volume in the total loan portfolio of banks decreased to 3.5%.

It is known that the quality of bank loans is one of the important indicators describing the state of the banking system and the economy. According to international experts, an increase in the share of problem assets in the gross loan portfolio from 10-15% indicates a systemic crisis in the banking sector.

A bank's loan portfolio, which encompasses all loans and advances extended to borrowers and recorded on the balance sheet, serves as the main source of revenue and is crucial for the bank's sustainability [8].

It is worth noting that the share of problem assets in the gross assets of the commercial banks of our republic decreased compared to previous years as of January 1, 2024, and the share of NPLs in the credit portfolio of commercial banks was 3.5%, which is a positive situation. Because problem assets do not bring income to the bank.

Analysis of the current state of overdue loans is carried out using the net loans indicator. As we know, net loans mean the part of "gross" loans reduced by the amount of reserve allocations. Net loans show the amount of loans that are actually active, that is, they are earning interest. The amount of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans indicates the amount of non-performing loans.

High levels of NPLs can weaken the financial health and stability of banks and financial institutions [9]. Non-performing loans tie up capital that could otherwise be used for productive lending activities, impairing liquidity, and solvency [10]. By reducing the share of NPLs, banks can enhance their resilience to economic shocks, maintain adequate capital buffers, and ensure the stability of the financial system.

Non-performing loans can impede credit availability and constrain lending to households and businesses [11]. Banks may become more risk-averse and reluctant to extend credit to borrowers, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and individuals with limited credit history. By reducing NPLs, banks can free up resources for new lending, stimulate investment and consumption, and support economic growth.

Managing non-performing loans is costly for banks, requiring resources for loan workout, restructuring, and recovery efforts. NPL resolution involves legal expenses, administrative costs, and potential write-offs, which can erode profitability and shareholder value. Decreasing the share of NPLs reduces the burden on banks, improves cost efficiency, and enhances overall profitability.

The removal of overdue loans from the balance sheet also reduces the weight of loans in gross assets. Because when the loan is removed from the balance, the opened loan account is credited, and the interest income or retained earnings account is debited. In the banking practice of our republic, the management of a commercial bank and the supervisory board of a bank can remove overdue loans from the bank's balance sheet.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Strengthening credit risk assessment processes is essential for preventing the emergence of new non-performing loans. Banks should improve their underwriting standards, conduct thorough credit analysis, and assess borrowers' creditworthiness rigorously. This involves evaluating factors such as income stability, repayment capacity, collateral quality, and borrower's track record.

Implementing early warning systems helps banks identify potential problem loans at an early stage, allowing them to take proactive measures to prevent deterioration. Early warning indicators may include changes in borrower behavior, deteriorating financial performance, industry-specific risks, or macroeconomic factors. By monitoring these indicators, banks can intervene promptly and mitigate credit risk.

For existing non-performing loans, banks can implement loan workout and restructuring strategies to rehabilitate troubled assets and restore borrower solvency. This may involve renegotiating loan terms, extending repayment periods, reducing interest rates, or providing financial assistance to distressed borrowers. Loan workout programs aim to maximize recovery while minimizing losses for both the bank and the borrower.

Banks can expedite NPL resolution by disposing of distressed assets through sales, auctions, or securitization transactions. Asset disposal allows banks to offload non-performing loans from their balance sheets, recover partial or full value, and redeploy capital to more productive uses. Asset recovery efforts may involve collaborating with debt collection agencies, engaging in foreclosure proceedings, or pursuing legal action against defaulting borrowers.

Adequate loan loss provisioning is essential for banks to cover potential losses associated with non-performing loans. Banks should assess the adequacy of their provisions regularly and adjust reserves based on changes in credit quality, economic conditions, and regulatory requirements. Proactive provisioning ensures that banks have sufficient buffers to absorb losses and maintain financial stability.

Implementing robust risk management frameworks helps banks identify, assess, and mitigate credit risk effectively. This involves establishing clear risk appetite statements, defining risk limits, conducting stress testing, and enhancing portfolio diversification. By incorporating risk management best practices into their operations, banks can reduce the incidence of non-performing loans and strengthen their overall risk resilience.

Banks should pursue debt recovery and legal remedies aggressively to recover outstanding amounts from delinquent borrowers. This may involve engaging in negotiations, initiating legal proceedings, or enforcing collateral rights to recover defaulted loans. Effective debt recovery practices help banks maximize recovery rates, minimize losses, and deter future delinquencies.

Investing in staff training and capacity building is crucial for equipping bank employees with the skills, knowledge, and tools necessary to manage non-performing loans effectively. Training programs may cover areas such as credit risk management, loan restructuring techniques, negotiation skills, and legal aspects of debt recovery. By empowering employees with the right expertise, banks can improve their NPL resolution capabilities and enhance operational efficiency.

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